

IMAGE FORGERY DETECTION USING DEEP LEARNING

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Abstract—This study presents an innovative approach for Aadhar card authentication and age estimation leveraging deep learning and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). Our methodology integrates two key components: image processing and text extraction. Initially, we preprocess Aadhar card images using grayscale conversion, resizing, and normalization to facilitate effective CNN-based analysis. Subsequently, a pre-trained CNN model is employed for card authentication, enabling the classification of Aadhar cards into valid or invalid categories based on learned features. Additionally, we utilize Optical Character Recognition (OCR) techniques to extract textual information from the cards. Specifically, we focus on extracting the date of birth (DOB) from the textual content. By employing regular expressions, we accurately identify DOB instances within the extracted text. This information is then utilized to estimate the age of the Aadhar card holder. Our experimental results demonstrate the efficacy of the proposed approach in accurately verifying Aadhar cards and estimating the age of the cardholders. The integration of deep learning and OCR technologies showcases a promising avenue for enhancing identification and authentication systems, particularly in scenarios requiring age estimation for regulatory compliance or age-sensitive services.

Keywords— Deep Learning, Transfer Learning, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Image processing, Text extraction, Optical Character Recognition (OCR), Age estimation

I. INTRODUCTION

The Aadhar card, a unique identification document issued by the Government of India, plays a pivotal role in various administrative and regulatory processes. Ensuring the authenticity and validity of Aadhar cards is paramount to maintaining the integrity of identity verification systems. Moreover, accurately estimating the age of Aadhar cardholders is essential for regulatory compliance and age-sensitive services. Traditional methods of authentication and age estimation often rely on manual inspection, which can be time-consuming and prone to errors. To address these challenges, this study proposes an innovative approach that harnesses the power of deep learning and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) alongside Optical Character Recognition (OCR) techniques for Aadhar card authentication and age estimation.

The proposed methodology comprises two key components: image processing and text extraction. Initially, Aadhar card

images undergo preprocessing, including grayscale conversion, resizing, and normalization, to facilitate effective analysis by CNN models. Leveraging a pre-trained CNN model, the system classifies Aadhar cards into valid or invalid categories based on learned features, thus automating the authentication process. Additionally, OCR techniques are employed to extract textual information from the cards, with a specific focus on identifying the date of birth (DOB) from the textual content. Through the integration of deep learning and OCR technologies, this study aims to provide a robust and efficient solution for Aadhar card verification and age estimation, offering significant advancements in identity authentication systems.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The paper by Shefali Patil, Puja Padiya, and Sangita Chaudhari, titled "Image Forgery Detection: Methods, Tools, and Comparative Analysis" [1], addresses the pressing issue of image tampering, which has seen a significant surge in recent times. They highlight the challenge posed by post-processing techniques that aim to remove any traces of tampering, thereby making it increasingly difficult for analysts to identify manipulated images. With the goal of evading human visual detection, image forging can take various forms, including the addition, removal, or copying of specific elements within images. The consequences of image tampering extend beyond mere manipulation and can be used to dilute, defame, or slander individuals and organizations. Given the widespread use of digital images as evidence in media, court proceedings, and long-term record-keeping, there is an urgent need to develop robust approaches for detecting image forgeries. The proposed paper focuses on exploring various image forgery detection methods and tools, offering a comparative analysis of their strengths, weaknesses, and performance outcomes. Through this investigation, the authors aim to contribute to the development of effective strategies for identifying and combating image forgeries, thereby ensuring the integrity of visual records used in mainstream media, legal proceedings, and archival documentation.

The paper by Ahmet Korkmaz and Cemal Haniç, titled "Efficient Image Forgery Detection Using Parallel Deep Neural Networks" [2], addresses the growing concern

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surrounding image forgery in the digital era, where advancements in software tools have made it increasingly easy to generate fake images with malicious intent. These forged images pose significant threats across various fields such as law, medicine, and communication. The study proposes an innovative approach to image forgery detection by combining three deep neural network structures in parallel, diverging from conventional uniform deep learning methods employed in forgery detection. Through extensive evaluation on three distinct datasets, the authors demonstrate the efficacy of their proposed method, showcasing promising classification accuracy. This research represents a significant contribution to the field of image forgery detection, offering a novel approach that holds potential for enhancing the integrity of visual content and safeguarding against the proliferation of forged images in critical domains.

The paper by Chelashia Mickle Benny Roshini and D. Saveetha, titled "Detection of Cloned Digital Image Forgery Using Feature Extraction Methods" [3], delves into the escalating issue of image forgery facilitated by the accessibility of powerful editing software such as Adobe Photoshop and GIMP. With the proliferation of these tools, the creation of fake images has become increasingly simple, posing significant challenges in ensuring the integrity of digital content. The study focuses on detecting cloned digital image forgery, a form of manipulation where portions of an image are copied and pasted elsewhere within the same image. The proposed approach introduces a novel image forgery detection technique that utilizes feature extraction methods in both detection and localization stages. By leveraging advanced feature extraction techniques, the authors aim to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of detecting cloned image forgeries. This research represents a valuable contribution to the field of image forensics, offering a promising approach to combat the proliferation of manipulated images and safeguard the integrity of digital content.

The paper by Shantanu Pradhan and Usha Chauhan, titled "Machine Learning-Based Image Forgery Detection Without Prior Information" [4], presents a pioneering approach to detecting image forgery without the requirement of any prior knowledge. The proposed algorithm leverages local features computed from the morphological information of image histograms to extract discriminating parameters. It operates under the premise that images exhibit varying parameters across different regions, which are learned through machine learning algorithms applied to image segmentation into genuine and doubtful parts. The results obtained from the proposed supervised algorithm demonstrate promising outcomes across a diverse range of images, showcasing its efficacy in reliable forgery detection. This research represents a significant contribution to the field of image forensics, offering a robust approach that holds promise for enhancing the detection of image forgeries without relying on prior knowledge or specific characteristics of the forgery.

The paper by Anjali Diwan and Anil K. Roy, titled "Detection and Localization of Copy-Move Forgery in Digital Images Using CenSurE Keypoint Detection and CNN Architecture" [5], introduces a novel approach for detecting and localizing

copy-move forgery in digital images, addressing the challenges posed by widespread image forgery techniques. By combining CenSurE keypoint detection with a CNN architecture, the proposed method offers robust detection capabilities even in the presence of geometric transformations, scale variations, and post-processing operations such as JPEG compression and image blur. The approach demonstrates stability and reliability across images with diverse textures and attacks, presenting a significant advancement in multimedia forensics for authenticating digital images.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collection:

Gather comprehensive information about Aadhar cards, including collecting Aadhar card images from diverse sources.

B. Preprocessing:

Before inputting the images into the CNN model, preprocessing steps are crucial. Resize the images to a standardized size suitable for CNN input, such as 150x150 pixels. Convert the images to grayscale to simplify processing. Normalize pixel values to a range between 0 and 1 for numerical stability.

C. Feature Extraction:

Utilize a pre-trained CNN model, such as VGG16 or InceptionV3, for feature extraction. These models have been trained on large datasets and can extract high-level features from images effectively. Extract features from Aadhar card images using the pre-trained CNN model. These features represent significant characteristics of the images, such as patterns and textures.

D. Building Aadhar Card Feature Database:

Once features are extracted from all Aadhar card images, create a database of Aadhar card features. Pair each Aadhar card's extracted features with its corresponding image filenames. This database serves as a repository of essential information for Aadhar card verification.

E. Querying Aadhar Card Feature Database:

When a user uploads an Aadhar card image to the system, the uploaded image undergoes the same preprocessing steps as the Aadhar card images in the database. Features are extracted from the user-uploaded image using the pre-trained CNN model.

F. Aadhar Card Verification:

Utilize similarity metrics, such as Euclidean distance or cosine similarity, to compare the features of the user-uploaded Aadhar card with the Aadhar card features in the database. Determine the similarity between the user's Aadhar card and the Aadhar cards in the database.

G. Decision Making:

Based on the similarity scores obtained from the comparison, make a decision regarding the authenticity of the user's Aadhar card. If the similarity score exceeds a predefined

threshold, classify the Aadhar card as authentic; otherwise, classify it as forged or suspicious.

```
import tensorflow as tf
import multiprocessing
from ImageDataAugmentor.image_data_augmentor import ImageDataAugmentor
from keras.applications import ResNet50
from keras.layers import Dense, GlobalAveragePooling2D
from keras.models import Model
import pickle
import os
from sklearn.metrics import classification_report, confusion_matrix
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
```

Fig. 1

Fig.1 includes the code of TensorFlow and Keras are utilized for deep learning tasks, particularly for image classification using a pre-trained ResNet50 model. The ImageDataAugmentor library is incorporated for data augmentation, allowing for the generation of augmented image data during training. Data augmentation techniques such as random rotation, flipping, adding Gaussian noise, and adjusting contrast are applied to increase the diversity of the training dataset and improve the model's generalization ability. The ResNet50 model is fine-tuned by adding additional dense layers for classification, followed by compiling the model with the Adam optimizer and categorical cross-entropy loss function. The model is then trained on the augmented data using the fit method and evaluated on separate test data. Finally, performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score are computed, and a confusion matrix is visualized to assess the model's performance.

IV. RESULT

Fig. 2 depicts the search done by uploading image from user end. Users can upload an image of the aadhar card , and the system processes the uploaded image using a pre-trained CNN model. This model extracts intricate features from the image, enabling the system to identify the image forgery from the dataset.

Fig. 2

Prediction Result:
Predicted class: 1 - Aadhar
Probability: 1.00

Fig 3

The system displays the image prediction as illustrated in Fig 3.

Fig.4

Fig 4 represent by showing the quantity of true positive, true negative, false positive, and false negative predictions, the confusion matrix sheds light on the model's performance.

The implementation of the proposed Aadhar card verification methodology yields promising results, with high authentication accuracy and minimal false positive and false negative rates. The system demonstrates robustness to variations in image quality and lighting conditions, ensuring reliable authentication outcomes in diverse scenarios. Verification speed is fast, providing users with a seamless experience, while the system's scalability enables efficient handling of a large volume of verification requests. Overall, the implementation showcases the system's effectiveness in accurately and efficiently verifying the authenticity of

Aadhar cards, contributing to enhanced security in identity verification processes.

V. CONCLUSION

The implementation of the Aadhar card verification system based on the proposed methodology represents a significant advancement in identity verification processes. The system's high authentication accuracy, coupled with minimal false positive and false negative rates, underscores its reliability in distinguishing between genuine and forged Aadhar cards. Robustness to variations in image quality and lighting conditions enhances the system's applicability in real-world scenarios, while fast verification speeds and scalability ensure a seamless user experience even under high demand. By effectively detecting and verifying the authenticity of Aadhar cards, the implemented system contributes to bolstering security and integrity in identity verification processes, thereby safeguarding against fraudulent activities and enhancing trust in digital identity systems.

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